

Numerical algorithm to reproduce bifurcation figures

Description:

Pseudocode to reproduce figures 10,11,12,13 of manuscript number **EPJS-D-25-00637R3**.

- In figures 10(a), 10(b), 11(a), 11(b), 12(a), 12(b), 13(a) and 13(b), the time is taken as autonomous
- In figures 10(c), 10(d), 11(c), 11(d), 12(c), 12(d), 13(c) and 13(d) the time is taken as nonautonomous

The parameter set is mentioned in the manuscript.

The figures 2, 3 and 5 are drawn using MATCONT software in Matlab.

Pseudocode 1 Parameter continuation and bifurcation detection via extrema analysis

- 1: **Input:** Initial state \mathbf{z}_0 , time step Δt , final time T
 - 2: **Input:** Continuation parameter $\alpha \in [\alpha_{\min}, \alpha_{\max}]$
 - 3: **Input:** Number of parameter samples p , tail length m , tolerance ε
 - 4: Construct time grid/interval for integration and parameter grid with p equidistance points.
 - 5: **for** $j = 1$ to p **do**
 - 6: Set $\alpha = \alpha_j$
 - 7: Integrate the system numerically to obtain solution matrix.
 - 8: Extract last m values of bifurcation variable, say $X(t)$.
 - 9: **if** $\max(X) - \min(X) < \varepsilon$ **then**
 - 10: Plot equilibrium point $(\alpha_j, X_{\text{end}})$
 - 11: **else**
 - 12: Identify all local extrema of $X(t)$
 - 13: Plot $(\alpha_j, X_{\text{extrema}})$
 - 14: **end if**
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: **Output:** Bifurcation diagram of equilibria and oscillatory extrema
-

Pseudocode 2 Computation of Lyapunov exponent

- 1: **Input:** Parameter range $\{T_j\}_{j=1}^{N_T}$
- 2: **Input:** Initial state \mathbf{x}_0
- 3: **Input:** Time step Δt , transient time T_{tr} , calculation time T_{cal}
- 4: Initialize arrays for the first and second Lyapunov exponents
- 5: **for** $j = 1$ to N_T **do**
- 6: Set continuation parameter $T = T_j$
- 7: Initialize state $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_0$
- 8: Initialize orthonormal perturbation matrix $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{I}$
- 9: Integrate the system for T_{tr} to eliminate transients
- 10: Initialize Lyapunov sum vector $\boldsymbol{\ell} = \mathbf{0}$
- 11: **for** $k = 1$ to $T_{\text{cal}}/\Delta t$ **do**
- 12: Evolve the reference trajectory using a fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme
- 13: Evolve perturbed trajectories using finite differences
- 14: Construct the perturbation growth matrix
- 15: Apply QR decomposition to reorthonormalize perturbations
- 16: Accumulate growth rates using logarithms of diagonal elements
- 17: **end for**
- 18: Compute Lyapunov exponents by time averaging
- 19: Sort exponents in descending order
- 20: Store the largest and second largest exponents
- 21: **end for**
- 22: Plot Lyapunov exponents as functions of the continuation parameter
- 23: Draw a reference zero line to identify stability transitions
- 24: **Output:** Largest and second largest Lyapunov exponents
